

Experimental Investigation of Processing Parameters on Porosity in Continuous Lattice Fabrication

Martin Eichenhofer¹, Joanna. C. H. Wong¹, Paolo Ermanni¹

¹ ETH Zurich, Laboratory of Composite Materials and Adaptive Structures, Tannenstrasse 3, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland

Keywords: Additive Manufacturing (AM), Fiber Composite Extrusion, Thermoplastic Composites

ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing (AM), also known as 3D printing, is an emerging and potentially revolutionary technology aimed at small volume manufacturing for highly customized applications, e.g. aerospace, medical devices, and replacement parts. However, the processing technology still requires development before it can be used to manufacture final parts beyond mere prototypes. The AM of continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites, in particular, presents its own set of challenges compared to processes that work with neat polymers, metals, and ceramics due to the anisotropy of the material. Existing state of the art technologies do not adequately address the issues of material quality and three-dimensionality (fibre orientation out of plane), and as a result, the great potential of these materials to produce high load bearing structures has not been fully realized.

Continuous lattice fabrication (CLF) – a novel additive manufacturing technique invented for the cost efficient deposition of fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites – exploits the anisotropic material properties while digitally fabricating structures. In contrast to the layer-by-layer approaches employed in most AM processes, CLF enables the directed orientation of the fibers in all spatial coordinates, that is, in the x-, y-, and z-directions.

As part of ongoing efforts to improve the mechanical properties of the materials produced by CLF, this study presents novel experimental results from investigations into the void growth observed during extrusion of thermoplastic fiber composite rods previously consolidated by pultrusion. Investigations showed that the void content of the extrudate was highly sensitive to the processing conditions and the geometrical dimensions of the extrusion die. Depending on the processing settings, void contents between 0.3% and 7.4% were measured. Understanding of the mechanisms that occur at the extrusion outlet which lead to increased void content is essential for developing processing strategies that minimize voids and improve mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

The emergence of additive manufacturing (AM) techniques, such as fused deposition modelling (FDM), selective laser sintering (SLS), and continuous liquid interface production (CLIP), enables new ways in lightweight design due to their ability to manufacture geometrically complex parts by selectively depositing material where it is needed, e.g. to support specific load distributions [1-3]. State-of-the-art AM techniques, like those mentioned above, are able to achieve complex three-dimensional structures by depositing successive layers of material to gradually build thickness in the third dimension. While layer-by-layer processes may be suitable for creating complex structures from isotropic materials, such as polymers, ceramics, metals, and biomaterials [4,5], whose properties are not dependent on directionality, these approaches lack the ability to control the orientation of materials in the third dimension, i.e. z-direction, and are thus inappropriate for harnessing the full potential of anisotropic materials, in particular continuous fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP), in engineering structures. The ability to apply layer-by-layer deposition techniques to continuous fiber reinforced polymers by integrating fibers into FDM processes has been demonstrated by several groups [6-10]. However, the ability to

strategically orient the fibers along load paths in all spatial directions is essential to fully exploit the excellent, but anisotropic, mechanical properties of continuous FRPs in lightweight designs [11-14].

In contrast to the layer-by-layer approaches employed in most AM processes, Continuous lattice fabrication (CLF) – a novel and patented additive manufacturing (AM) technique invented for the cost efficient deposition of continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites [15] – enables the directed orientation of the fibers in all spatial coordinates, that is in the x-, y-, and z-directions. The proof-of-concept of the technology was first demonstrated and presented at the ICCM20 conference in Copenhagen by the contribution titled “Analysis of processing conditions for a novel 3D-composite production technique” [16]; further details about the CLF process have been reported in a manuscript titled “Continuous Lattice Fabrication of Ultra-Lightweight Composite Structures” which is currently under review for publication by Additive Manufacturing, Elsevier. As part of ongoing efforts to improve the mechanical properties of the materials produced by CLF, this study presents novel experimental results from investigations into the void growth observed in consolidated pultruded rods obtained upon reheating in the extrusion nozzle.

Understanding of the mechanisms at the extrusion outlet that lead to increased porosity is essential for developing processing strategies that minimize voids and improve mechanical properties. In thermoplastic composite materials, residual stresses are primarily caused by shear alignment of the viscoelastic polymer matrix [17,18], thermal expansion [19,20], fiber compaction [21,22], crystallization [23,24] and pressurization of gas-filled bubbles [25,26], and represent energy, which is stored inside the solidified polymer matrix. In most conventional thermoplastic composite processes, e.g. pultrusion, stamp forming, etc. [27], the residual stresses are stored in the composite in the form of elastic energy by consolidation and instant cooling. However, when the material is remelted upon reheating, the stored energy is released resulting in void growth [19,20,28]. Therefore, the understanding of processing conditions while reheating a consolidated FRP material is essential to preserve the extrudate quality, this is particularly important for the AM of thermoplastic FRP materials. The aim of the following investigation is to identify processing effects due to reheating of the consolidated thermoplastic rod in the extrusion module.

2 MATERIALS

Seven commingled yarns (CDC 41815, Schappe Technologies, France) consisting of 52% v/v stretch broken carbon fibers (STS40, Toho Tenax, Japan) and 48% v/v melt spun polyamide 12 (PA12, EMS Chemie, Switzerland) polymer fibers with a tex number of 313 were consolidated into a thermoplastic rod of 1.40mm diameter by the CLF pultrusion module. This rod was consequently used as preconsolidated intermediate material for the CLF extrusion module. The relevant material properties are provided in Tab. 1.

material	property	abbreviation	unit	value
STS40 fiber	tensile strength	σ_f	<i>MPa</i>	4000
STS40 fiber	tensile modulus	E_f	<i>GPa</i>	240
STS40 fiber	maximum elongation	ε_f	%	1.73
STS40 fiber	density	ρ_f	<i>kg/m³</i>	1770
PA12 matrix	tensile strength	σ_m	<i>MPa</i>	55
PA12 matrix	tensile modulus	E_m	<i>GPa</i>	1.27
PA12 matrix	maximum elongation	ε_m	%	33
PA12 matrix	density	ρ_m	<i>kg/m³</i>	1010
PA12/STS40 yarn	fibre volume content	ν_f	%	52
PA12/STS40 yarn	matrix volume content	ν_m	%	48
PA12/STS40 yarn	fibre weight content	w_f	%	66
PA12/STS40 yarn	matrix weight content	w_m	%	34
PA12/STS40 yarn	tex number	<i>tex</i>	<i>g/km</i>	313
PA12/STS40 rod	number of yarns	<i>n</i>	–	7
PA12/STS40 rod	rod diameter	<i>d</i>	<i>mm</i>	1.40
PA12/STS40 rod	fibre volume content	ν_f	%	52
PA12/STS40 rod	matrix volume content	ν_m	%	48
PA12/STS40 rod	fibre weight content	w_f	%	66
PA12/STS40 rod	matrix weight content	w_m	%	34
PA12/STS40 rod	density	ρ_{rod}	<i>kg/m³</i>	1405

Table 1: Material properties of unconsolidated feedstock material and the consolidated thermoplastic rod.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Process description and conditions

As described by Eichenhofer et al. in the manuscript titled “Continuous Lattice Fabrication of Ultra-Lightweight Composite Structures” (currently under review at the Additive Manufacturing Journal, Elsevier), Continuous lattice fabrication (CLF) consists of a serial pultrusion and extrusion system (see Fig. 1A) allowing for the in situ consolidation of low-priced unconsolidated intermediate materials, e.g. commingled yarns, and an in situ deposition of the fully consolidated extrudate. Incoming feedstock material is pulled through a pre-heating module where the material is partially melted in preparation for consolidation. Impregnation, consolidation and cooling occurs in the pultrusion module, which contains a temperature-controlled tapered die, forming a solid thermoplastic rod. The fully consolidated material is then fed into a temperature-controlled extrusion module similar to those used in FDM, where it is reheated and discharged from the processing head in the form of a consolidated, yet pliable, extrudate. In this way, the fiber-reinforced thermoplastic extrudate can be continuously shaped as it exits the nozzle through the relative movement of the extrusion head with respect to a fixed point, e.g. substrate. This relative displacement may be achieved by moving the extruder head, by repositioning the substrate, or a combination of both (see Fig. 1B). In CLF, a robotic arm is used to move the extruder head over a stationary substrate. Upon contact with the ambient air, the extruded material cools and eventually solidifies.

In this study, thermoplastic fiber composite rods were processed solely by the CLF pultrusion module at a constant pultrusion speed of 105 mm/min and at 250°C to create a consolidated thermoplastic rod. Those initially fabricated rods were used in this study as feedstock material for the investigation on void growth in the extrusion module. This ensures the isolation of processing effects originating from the pultrusion module from those of the extrusion module. The temperature of the extrusion stage was set to 230°C and the extrusion speeds were varied from 0-300mm/min, where 0mm/min represents the stationary condition, i.e. extrusion process was stopped while the extrudate still remains in the extrusion nozzle. Cooling of the discharged extrudate is mainly achieved by convective cooling with the ambient

air which has a temperature of approximately 23°C.

Figure 1: CLF provides an in situ consolidation of cost efficient intermediate materials for thermoplastic composites. (A) Schematic of the CLF modular processing head. (B) Extrudate shape is determined by the relative movement between the CLF processing head and the base substrate in three-dimensional space.

3.2 Material characterization

A differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) machine (DSC 1, STAR System, Mettler Toledo) was used to determine the thermal response of the material. The reversing curve of an alternating differential scanning calorimetry (ADSC) measurement was used to determine the specific heat capacity. A temperature sweep from 25°C to 190°C with a total of 16 steps at a heating rate of 5K/min and a stepwise inclination of 20K positive and 10K negative was performed to determine the heat flow rate. The effects of the sample holder were removed by subtracting the curve of a blank (empty) specimen. The specific heat capacity was derived by dividing the heat flow rate by the mass of the sample and the heating rate.

The transverse thermal conductivity was measured on a 50mm x 50mm x 12mm specimen using a custom developed guarded hot plate device designed for low thermal conductivity materials.

Optical microscopy was used to determine the void contents of the CLF extrudates. To prepare the samples for characterization, test specimens were embedded in resin (SpeciFix 20, Struers, USA) and polished (Abramin, Struers, Denmark) using coarse and fine grained grinding discs (MD Piano 120 to MD Nap, Struers, Denmark) in the presence of polishing suspensions (DiaPro Allegro/Largo 9 µm to Diapro Nap R 1 µm) to obtain smooth cross-sectional areas. Digital images of the polished specimens were taken using an optical microscope (DM RXA, Leica, Germany). These digital images were then analyzed by using a software package (Leica QWin, Leica, Germany) to differentiate and calculate the fractional area occupied by voids. A total of at least 5 individual images for each processing configuration were analyzed to quantify the void content values presented in this study.

3.3 Thermal simulation of extrusion process

A conjugated heat transfer simulation was created in Comsol Multiphysics, in order to quantify the net energy intake, i.e. energy flow into the rod while passing through the extrusion nozzle. The model consists of a rigid body extrusion nozzle made of brass and a boundary representation in which a fluid body may undergo laminar flow. The nozzle dimensions and the implemented material characteristics are provided in Tab. 2, where the interaction length represents the contact area between extrudate and nozzle.

property	unit	value
interaction length	<i>mm</i>	3.5
extrusion diameter	<i>mm</i>	1.40/1.45
heat conductivity brass	<i>W/mK</i>	120
heat conductivity air	<i>W/mK</i>	0.05
heat conductivity extrudate (longitudinal)	<i>W/mK</i>	8.95
heat conductivity extrudate (transverse)	<i>W/mK</i>	0.58
heat transfer coefficient air-extrudate	<i>W/m²K</i>	130 [29]

Table 2: Nozzle dimensions and implemented material characteristics for conjugated heat transfer model in Comsol Multiphysics.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Measured heat capacity of extrudate

A melting temperature T_m of 176.56°C was measured from the heating cycle of the DSC recording. No clear glass transition temperature was found. The specific heat capacity measured from the reversing curve of the ADSC test is depicted in Fig. 2 and provided the input values for the specific heat capacity of the composite materials in the numerical simulations.

Figure 2: Recorded specific heat capacity of PA12/STS40 fiber composite material.

4.2 Measured thermal conductivity of extrudate

The thermal conductivity measurement yielded a thermal conductivity transverse to the fiber direction of $\lambda_{rod,trans} = 0.58 \pm 0.06 \frac{W}{mK}$ at $T=22.5^{\circ}C$. Further considerations for the thermal conductivity along the fiber direction led to a calculated value of $8.9539 \frac{W}{mK}$ by applying the rule of mixture and reported values for the PA12 ($0.22 \frac{W}{mK}$) and the STS40 carbon fibers ($17 \frac{W}{mK}$) [30]. Thomann et al. [30] showed an empirical approach to calculate the temperature dependency of the thermal conductivity for a unidirectional plate using an Eshelby tensor. The calculated temperature deviation is significantly lower than the measured 10% deviation for the transverse thermal conductivity and hence, the conductivities are kept constant for all further investigations within this work.

4.3 Initial void content of consolidated feedstock material

The initial void content of the consolidated thermoplastic rods after pultrusion was measured to be 0.65% v/v under fixed processing conditions. This value was taken to be the baseline void content against which the extruded material was compared.

4.4 Influence of extrusion speed on void growth

The experimental investigation to determine the influence of extrusion speed on void growth in pultruded thermoplastic composite rods showed a significant increase in void content upon reheating. Multiple pultruded thermoplastic composite rods were processed through the CLF extrusion nozzle at different extrusion speeds to measure the void growth upon reheating. Fig. 3 shows the results of the experimental void growth characterization and compares the findings to the baseline void content of the pultruded intermediate material. At low extrusion speeds, high void contents ($> 7\%$) were measured. A sharp drop in void growth was observed between extrusion speeds 50 mm/min and 100 mm/min. No significant deviation from the baseline was detected for extrusion speeds exceeding 100mm/min.

Evaluations of cross sectional images showed that void sizes were significantly greater in samples extruded at lower speeds. This is explained by the higher total thermal energy transfer that takes place during the extended interaction period between the heated nozzle and the pultruded rods. In the remelted material, pressurized air entrapments are able to expand at elevated temperatures and reduced pressure of the extrusion nozzle. A correlation between extrusion speed and measured void content was found, which can be explained by the amount of heat conveyed by heat conduction at the contact area of the extrusion nozzle.

Figure 3: Results of experimental characterization on void growth in the CLF extrusion module. Nozzle diameter 1.45mm, composite rod diameter 1.40mm.

4.5 Influence of geometrical conditions on void growth

The correlation between geometry of the extrusion nozzle, in particular the gap between the extrusion nozzle and the extrudate, and the void growth seen in Fig. 3 was investigated by changing the diameter of the extrusion die while maintaining the same pultrusion settings. A schematic of the two extrusion conditions is provided in Fig. 4, where the extrudate can be seen to be heated under physically constrained and unconstrained conditions.

Figure 4: Schematic to illustrate the geometrical conditions within the extrusion die, i.e. geometrically constrained extrudate and geometrically unconstrained extrudate.

The results of the void content measurements for the different configurations show a clear dependency on the geometrical constraints of the extrusion die, see Fig. 5. The maximum void content seems to relate to the free space between nozzle and extrudate (gap). Specimens fabricated under zero

gap conditions showed no deterioration of the extrudate quality in terms of increasing void contents.

Void measurements showed that the onset of void growth can be completely suppressed by intimate contact between extrusion nozzle and extrudate, leading to the assumption that the discharged extrudate with continuous fiber strands is restrained simultaneously by geometrical containment and instant cooling. Solidification of the outmost polymeric material restrains the expansion of pressurized voids and mitigates the effects of residual stresses.

Figure 5: Relationship between void growth and geometrical conditions of extrusion die in the unconstrained case (blue) and constrained case (red).

4.6 Energy boundary limit for void growth

In order to generalize the findings presented above, a simulation model of the extrusion process was implemented in Comsol Multiphysics to determine the net energy conveyed into the extrudate while passing through the extrusion die. Recordings with a thermographic camera (IR thermocamera TESTO 885), were taken to validate the simulation. The emissivity of the camera was found at $\epsilon = 0.95$ by the use of a heating chamber (Heraeus UT6120) under controlled conditions of 230°C. Fig. 6 shows the superposition of the measured and the simulated surface temperatures, starting at the extrusion outlet. A acceptable agreement with the measured temperatures was achieved. Recordings show lower surface temperatures close to the extrusion outlet due to radiation of the hot body of the extrusion nozzle [31]. The validated simulation model was used to calculate the net energy intake of the extrudate while passing through the nozzle.

Fig. 7 depicts the findings of Fig. 3 as they relate to energy input as calculated from the simulation divided by the mass of the extrudate in the extrusion nozzle. Above an energy input of approximately 0.26 J/mg (critical energy boundary limit) a high increase in void content was found. Void contents over 7% were recorded above 0.38 J/mg, which corresponds to an averaged energy level of the extrudate at melting point of 176°C, determined for a 3.5 mm long section (contact area die) of the extrudate.

The amount of energy needed for the fiber filled melt to release the residual stresses, as observed by high void growth, was calculated to be close to the energy level at which the extrudate has a homogenous temperature close to melting temperature. However, the onset of void growth is initiated at lower energy levels, which is reasonable, as the void growth starts in the circumferential area of the rod and propagates inwards following the inhomogeneous temperature distribution of the cross sectional area. Highest

temperatures are reached first in the surface area and evolve over time inwards. The cross sectional images in Fig. 3 and the simulated temperature distributions in Fig. 7 support this explanation.

Figure 6: Infrared measurements (A) and numerical simulations (B) of extrudate surface temperature at a domain point probe with a 1mm distance from the extrusion outlet.

Figure 7: Results of numerical simulation for conveyed energy during the extrusion process and the correlation to the experimentally characterized void growth.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigated the effects of void growth in pultruded thermoplastic rods (PA12/STS40, 52% v/v) extruded under controlled processing conditions for a new additive manufacturing process for continuous fiber reinforced materials (CLF, ETH Zurich). Significant void growth (>7%) was detected for extrusions exceeding the critical energy boundary limit of approximately 0.26 J/mg. This is the energy conveyed to a 3.5mm long section of the rod under processing conditions. The origin of the void growth was explained by the mitigation of residual stresses due to the expansion of existing pressurized air entrapments in the pultruded thermoplastic feedstock material. No shear rate dependency or polymeric swelling effects, usually observed in neat polymer extrusion, were detected. Further investigation showed that void growth can be suppressed by geometrical containment of the extrudate within the extrusion nozzle paired with sufficient convective cooling at the exit of the extrusion die.

The gained understanding of the mechanisms at the extrusion outlet that lead to increased porosity will be used to develop processing strategies that minimize voids and improve mechanical properties in CLF processing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by ETH Zurich's internal research funding program (ETH Research Grant ETH-33 15-2) and the Commission for Technology and Innovation (CTI) through the Swiss Competence Center for Energy Research (SCCER) Efficient Technologies and Systems for Mobility. Commingled yarns were kindly provided by Schappe Technologies. Commingled yarns were kindly provided by Schappe Technologies. The authors thank Giovanni Cavolina for his support on characterization of the processing material and the Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology (EMPA) for access to their thermal conductivity measuring system.

REFERENCES

- [1] Raney JR, Lewis JA. Printing mesoscale architectures. *MRS Bull* 2015;40:943–50. doi:10.1557/mrs.2015.235.
- [2] Tumbleston JR, Shirvanyants D, Ermoshkin N, Janusziewicz R, Johnson AR, Kelly D, et al. Continuous liquid interface production of 3D objects. *Science* (80-) 2015;347.
- [3] Compton BG, Lewis JA. 3D-Printing of Lightweight Cellular Composites. *Adv Mater* 2014;26:5930–5. doi:10.1002/adma.201401804.
- [4] Lindemann C, Reiher T, Jahnke U, Koch R. Towards a sustainable and economic selection of part candidates for additive manufacturing. *Rapid Prototyp J* 2015;21:216–27. doi:10.1108/RPJ-12-2014-0179.
- [5] Zheng X, Lee H, Weisgraber TH, Shusteff M, DeOtte J, Duoss EB, et al. Ultralight, ultrastiff mechanical metamaterials. *Science* (80) 2014;344:1373 LP – 1377.
- [6] Tian X, Liu T, Yang C, Wang Q, Li D. Interface and performance of 3D printed continuous carbon fiber reinforced PLA composites. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2016;88:198–205. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.05.032.
- [7] Kumar S, Kruth J-P. Composites by rapid prototyping technology. *Mater Des* 2010;31:850–6. doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2009.07.045.
- [8] Wang X, Jiang M, Zhou Z, Gou J, Hui D. 3D printing of polymer matrix composites: A review and prospective. *Compos Part B Eng* 2017;110:442–58. doi:10.1016/j.compositesb.2016.11.034
- [9] Matsuzaki R, Ueda M, Namiki M, Jeong T-K, Asahara H, Horiguchi K, et al. Three-dimensional printing of continuous-fiber composites by in-nozzle impregnation. *Sci Rep* 2016;6:23058. doi:10.1038/srep23058.
- [10] Van Der Klift F, Koga Y, Todoroki A, Ueda M, Hirano Y, Matsuzaki R. 3D Printing of Continuous Carbon Fibre Reinforced Thermo-Plastic (CFRTP) Tensile Test Specimens. *Open J Compos Mater* 2016;06:18–27. doi:10.4236/ojcm.2016.61003.

- [11] Quan Z, Larimore Z, Wu A, Yu J, Qin X, Mirotznik M, et al. Microstructural design and additive manufacturing and characterization of 3D orthogonal short carbon fiber/acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene preform and composite. *Compos Sci Technol* 2016;126:139–48. doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2016.02.021.
- [12] Allen RJA, Trask RS. An experimental demonstration of effective Curved Layer Fused Filament Fabrication utilising a parallel deposition robot. *Addit Manuf* 2015;8:78–87. doi:10.1016/j.addma.2015.09.001.
- [13] Martin JJ, Fiore BE, Erb RM, Marshall SJ, Ritchie RO. Designing bioinspired composite reinforcement architectures via 3D magnetic printing. *Nat Commun* 2015;6:8641. doi:10.1038/ncomms9641.
- [14] Nakagawa Y, Mori K, Maeno T. 3D printing of carbon fibre-reinforced plastic parts. *Int J Adv Manuf Technol* 2017;1–7. doi:10.1007/s00170-016-9891-7.
- [15] Eichenhofer F, Eichenhofer M. Method for producing a framework. Patent Number WO2015169414A1.
- [16] Eichenhofer M, Wong J, Ermanni P. Analysis of processing conditions for a novel 3D composite production technique, Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Composites Materials, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19-24, 2015.
- [17] Russo G, Phillips TN. Numerical prediction of extrudate swell of branched polymer melts. *Rheol Acta* 2010;49:657–76. doi:10.1007/s00397-009-0426-0.
- [18] Seemork J, Siriprumpoonthum M, Lee Y, Nobukawa S, Yamaguchi M. Effect of Die Geometry on Drawdown Force of Polypropylene at Capillary Extrusion. *Adv Polym Technol* 2015;34:n/a – n/a. doi:10.1002/adv.21477.
- [19] Parlevliet PP, Bersee HEN, Beukers A. Residual stresses in thermoplastic composites—A study of the literature—Part I: Formation of residual stresses. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2006;37:1847–57. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2005.12.025.
- [20] Parlevliet PP, Bersee HEN, Beukers A. Residual stresses in thermoplastic composites—A study of the literature—Part II: Experimental techniques. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2007;38:651–65. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2006.07.002.
- [21] Ye L, Lu M, Mai Y-W. Thermal de-consolidation of thermoplastic matrix composites—I. Growth of voids. *Compos Sci Technol* 2002;62:2121–30. doi:10.1016/S0266-3538(02)00144-6.
- [22] Brzeski M, Mitschang P. Deconsolidation and its interdependent mechanisms of fibre reinforced polypropylene. *Polym Polym Compos* 2015;23:515–24. doi:10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004.
- [23] Chapman TJ, Gillespie JW, Pipes RB, Manson J-AE, Seferis JC. Prediction of Process-Induced Residual Stresses in Thermoplastic Composites. *J Compos Mater* 1990;24:616–43. doi:10.1177/002199839002400603.
- [24] Lawrence WE, Seferis JC, Gillespie JW. Material response of a semicrystalline thermoplastic polymer and composite in relation to process cooling history. *Polym Compos* 1992;13:86–96. doi:10.1002/pc.750130204.
- [25] Bernet N, Michaud V, Bourban PE, Manson JAE. An Impregnation Model for the Consolidation of Thermoplastic Composites Made from Commingled Yarns. *J Compos Mater* 1999;33:751–72. doi:10.1177/002199839903300806.
- [26] Gröschel C, Drummer D. The Influence of Moisture and Laminate Setup on the De-Consolidation Behavior of PA6/GF Thermoplastic Matrix Composites. *Int Polym Process* 2014;29:660–8. doi:10.3139/217.2976.
- [27] Vaidya UK, Chawla KK. Processing of fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites. *Int Mater Rev* 2008;53:185–218. doi:10.1179/174328008X325223.
- [28] Vaxman A, Narkis M, Siegmann A, Kenig S. Void formation in short-fiber thermoplastic composites. *Polym Compos* 1989;10:449–53. doi:10.1002/pc.750100609.
- [29] Domm M, Fischer J, Mitschang P. Development of an additive manufacturing process for the processing of continuous fiber reinforced polymers, Proceedings of the 17th European Conference on Composite Materials, Munich, Germany, June 26-30, 2016.

- [30] Thomann UI, Sauter M, Ermanni P. A combined impregnation and heat transfer model for stamp forming of unconsolidated commingled yarn preforms. *Compos Sci Technol* 2004;64:1637–51. doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2003.12.002.
- [31] TEGAM Inc., Advantages of contact thermometers over non-contact/infrared thermometers, <https://www.tegam.com/>, Geneva, Ohio, USA.